

Islamic Ethical Leadership: Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's Perspective on Governance and Its Relevance in Contemporary Nigerian Politics

Dr. Bello Muhammad¹, A. A. Umar²

^{1,2}Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State

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*Corresponding Author: Dr. Bello Muhammad

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Abstract

Original Research Article

Ethical leadership is the basis of a successful government but it has always been a challenge to Nigerian governance. This study looks closely at Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's view on ethical leadership and how it applies to contemporary Nigerian politics. Drawing from secondary sources, the study delves into Gumi's principles of justice, accountability and moral integrity through reflecting on Gumi's views as documented in his sermons, writings and teachings. Moreover, it looks at how well Gumi's ideas about ethical leadership fit with how contemporary Nigerian political leaders act. The study identifies key ethical principles highlighted by Sheikh Gumi and their potential to address the ethical crisis in Nigerian governance using a detailed analysis of secondary literature. The results show that Gumi's teachings firmly promote fair and just leadership, yet the way politics works in Nigeria today often goes against these beliefs. This study offers recommendations on how to integrate Gumi's moral ideas into political leadership training and public governance in Nigeria.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership, Governance, Nigerian Politics, Moral Integrity, Accountability, Islamic.

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INTRODUCTION

Ethical leadership is an important part of good governance especially in places where there is political instability and systemic corruption. The ongoing problems with unethical political behaviour in Nigeria have made it clear that we need leadership models based on moral integrity and accountability (Paden, 1986; Tsiga, 1992). Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi (1924–1992), a well-known Islamic scholar and reformer, gave an example of ethical leadership based on Islamic principles (Loimeier, 1997). His teachings stressed fairness, openness and the moral duties of leaders. These ideas are still relevant in Nigerian politics today (Gumi, 1984; Tsiga, 1992). Sheikh Gumi's work as the Grand Khadi of the Northern Region of Nigeria and his dedication to Islamic law had a significant impact on how he led (Paden, 1986). He advocate for a system of government in which leaders are not only good at politics but also morally upright, following the ethical principles of Islam (Loimeier, 1997). Gumi's insistence on including moral issues in political leadership went against the norms of his time and gave people a vision for a more fair and responsible way to run the government (Gumi, 1984). The purpose of this study is to critically examine Sheikh

Abubakar Gumi's views on moral leadership and see how they can be apply to Nigerian politics of today. The study analyse his sermons, writings and speeches in public to try to make clear the main ideas behind his ethical leadership model (Tsiga, 1992). Also, the study examines how Gumi's teachings can be used to fix the moral problems that are currently present in Nigeria's political scene. The purpose of this study is to add to the discussion about ethical governance and show how religiously informed leadership models could help make politics more honest.

Objective

The goal of this study is to critically look at Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's ideas about ethical leadership including their core values and how they apply to politics in Nigeria today. It also seeks to find out how Gumi's ideas about justice, responsibility and moral integrity can be used to deal with the moral problems in Nigeria's current political landscape.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Ethical Leadership:

Ethical leadership is a concept that has been thoroughly analysed in leadership studies. According to

Brown and Treviño (2006), it is the act of exhibiting normatively acceptable behaviour via one's own behaviour and interpersonal interactions. Setting the bar for moral conduct in their organisations and communities, ethical leaders place a high priority on virtues like honesty, integrity, justice and accountability. Also Yukl (2013) in his studies, asserted that ethical leadership involves not only making legally compliant decisions but also making sure that these decisions are morally sound taking into account the effects they will have on stakeholders and society as a whole. The need for leaders who embody moral values and act as role models for honesty and responsibility has been highlighted by Nigeria's ongoing problems with corruption and unethical governance (Fahm et al., 2024).

Islamic Perspectives on Ethical Leadership:

The Qur'an and the Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) teach that Islamic ethical leadership is based on key principles including fairness ('adl), trustworthiness (amānah), consultation (shūrā) and accountability (mas'ūliyyah) (Qur'an 4:58; Qur'an 16:90). These principles are the moral basis for Islamic government where being a leader is seen as a trust (amānah) instead of a privilege (Ali, 2005). In his role as a leader, the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) who is seen as the model of ethical leadership in Islam, prioritising servant leadership, humility and justice (Puteh Salin, 2021). Islamic thinkers like Al-Ghazali (2000) have gone into further detail about these ideas stressing that being a good leader is a moral duty that demands being accountable to both God and the people. Al-Ghazali says that leaders should be aware of God (taqwā) and make sure that their acts promote societal justice and wellbeing. In Nigeria, where there are still problems with governance, using Islamic moral values might help make things more open, accountable and fair (Fahm et al., 2024).

Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's Ethical Leadership Ideals:

Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi (1924–1992) was a well-known Islamic scholar, jurist and reformer. His ideas on moral leadership have had a huge effect on Nigeria's religious and political setting. Gumi was the Grand Khadi of the Northern Region of Nigeria. He utilised his power and influence to push for leadership based on Islamic moral values, focussing on fairness, responsibility, honesty and the well-being of the people (Loimeier, 1997; Tsiga, 1992). His ideas about ethical leadership show that he is very committed to the basic ideas of Islam and how they may be used in government. Justice was a key part of Sheikh Gumi's moral leadership ideology. He thought that leaders should be fair and not show favouritism or prejudice while making choices. The Qur'an says, "*Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice*" (4:58). This is how he understood justice. Gumi said that a leader who is not fair is not fit to lead since unfairness leads to anger, fighting and societal divisiveness (Gumi, 1984). Gumi's idea of justice went beyond fairness in the courts. He said that leaders must

make sure that resources and opportunities are fairly distributed. He spoke out against corruption, nepotism and using public position for personal benefit because he saw them as serious breaches of the values of justice and ethical leadership (Paden, 1986). Sheikh Gumi's ethical leadership ideology also included the principle of accountability. He used the prophetic tradition to say that every leader is a "shepherd" who is accountable for their followers: "*Each of you is a shepherd, and each of you is responsible for his flock*" (Sahih Bukhari, Hadith 6719). Gumi says that leaders need to know that they are responsible to the people they lead and, in the end, to God. He pushed for open government, where officials are accessible to criticism and often tell the public how they are doing their jobs. He thought that self-responsibility was just as important, and that leaders should always think about what they do and make sure it is in line with moral and ethical standards (Loimeier, 1997).

Sheikh Gumi will not compromise on honesty and integrity. He stressed that leaders should be honest, trustworthy, and true in what they say and do. This stance was in line with what the Qur'an says: "O you who have believed, fear Allah and speak words of appropriate justice" (Qur'an 33:70). Gumi thought that a leader's honesty was what made them trustworthy and gave them credibility. He spoke out against leaders who lied, were hypocritical or were corrupt, saying that this kind of behaviour not only destroys public trust but also brings God's retribution. Gumi believed that leadership was a sacred trust (amānah) and breaking that trust is a serious moral and spiritual crime (Gumi, 1984).

The idea of God-consciousness (taqwā) was at the centre of Sheikh Gumi's ideas about ethical leadership. He said that you cannot be a good ethical leader without feeling responsible to God. This feeling of being accountable to God makes sure that leaders stay honest even when others are not watching them. Gumi always told leaders that their authority was a gift from God and that they would have to answer to God for how they handled it. People who believed this were more likely to be humble, religious and willing to serve rather than rule (Tsiga, 1992). He also encouraged leaders to think about themselves and grow spiritually on a daily basis, saying that leaders who are spiritually grounded are less prone to do immoral things. Sheikh Gumi was a moral leader because he believed in servant leadership. He emphasised that leaders are not in charge of the people but rather servants who are responsible for the well-being of the society. This idea fits with the prophetic model of leadership which says that "*the finest leader is one who serves the people with honesty and humility*", as the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) said. Gumi said that leaders who see public service as a way to get money are bad leaders. He said that genuine leaders are those who put the needs of society before their own. He told leaders to be open to the people, listen to their complaints and strive hard to meet their demands (Loimeier, 1997).

One of Sheikh Gumi's most impressive traits was his willingness to tell the truth even when it was hard. He was not afraid to speak out against corrupt authorities or call out immoral behaviour, no matter who it was, whether

politicians, religious leaders or regular people. Gumi thought that moral bravery was necessary for ethical leadership. This means being willing to stand up for what is right even if it is unpopular or risky. He utilised his sermons and publications to promote moral leadership and social justice and he always used them to speak out against corruption, immorality and injustice. This bravery made him a revered advocate for justice and morality in Nigeria (Paden, 1986; Tsiga, 1992).

Sheikh Gumi's ideas about ethical leadership also included talking things over and making decisions as a group. He emphasised that leaders should not make choices on their own but instead should ask those who are experienced and trustworthy for advice. This method called *shūrā* in Islamic administration makes sure that choices are based on good information and the community's common knowledge. As a religious leader, Gumi routinely spoke with others before making big choices. He would ask intellectuals, community leaders and regular people for their opinions. He thought that leaders who do not ask for advice are more likely to make mistakes or make judgements that are not fair (Gumi, 1984).

Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's ideas about ethical leadership are still a good way to think about leadership especially in places where there is corruption, bad governance and bad leadership. His lessons on servant leadership, justice, accountability and integrity show leaders how to conduct in a way that is consistent with moral principles. Gumi's dedication to moral bravery, God-consciousness and consultation supports the concept that being an ethical leader is not just about who you are but also about your duty to God and the people.

Application of Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's Ethical Leadership in Contemporary Nigeria

The ethical leadership ideas of Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi, which were based on justice ('*adl*), accountability (*mas'ūliyyah*) and moral integrity are still relevant in Nigeria's social and political setting. His ideas on leadership provide a way to judge how current Nigerian leaders act and to comprehend the moral issues that still exist in the country's government. By examining the case studies of Nigerian leaders who align or conflict with Gumi's principles, this following provides a critical analysis of the ethical leadership crisis in Nigeria.

Case Studies of Nigerian Leaders in Relation to Gumi's Principles

1. Shehu Shagari: A Legacy of Good Intentions in the Face of Problems

Shehu Shagari was Nigeria's first executive president from 1979 to 1983. His government focused on industrialisation, economic growth and building more infrastructure. One of the most important projects was the Ajaokuta Steel Mill which was meant to help Nigeria's industry thrive (Akanji, 2019). Shagari started the "Ethical Revolution" in 1981 because he saw that society was becoming more immoral. The goal was to establish discipline and honesty in public service (Osaghae, 2011). He also set up the Ministry of National Guidance to

encourage Nigerians to act in a moral way (Joseph, 2014). Shagari's government had a lot of problems even with these efforts. The economy was becoming worse, oil prices were going down and there were claims of corruption among officials (Falola & Heaton, 2008). Shagari was found not guilty of corruption but the people lost faith in his government because of its perceived ethical problems. This led to a military coup in 1983 (Joseph, 2014). Sheikh Gumi's teachings stated that personal integrity is not enough on its own; there also has to be societal accountability and openness. This mixed legacy align with Gumi's teachings.

2. Umaru Musa Yar'Adua: Embodiment of Transparency and Rule of Law

Umaru Musa Yar'Adua was Nigeria's president from 2007 until his death in 2010. He was known for being honest and following the law. He was the first Nigerian president to openly declare his assets which set a standard for accountability (Gambari, 2013). The Amnesty Program for Niger Delta militants was started by Yar'Adua's government to promote peace and rehabilitation (Ukeje, 2014). His Seven Point Agenda concentrated on important areas like education, power and infrastructure, showing that he was dedicated to social fairness and national development (Yar'Adua, 2008). Yar'Adua's humble and welcoming leadership style fit with Gumi's ideas of servant leadership. His focus on due process and institutional changes showed how committed he was to ethical governance (Gambari, 2013). But his government was held down by health problems which made it hard for him to completely carry out his plans for reform.

3. Dora Akunyili: A fighter against Fake Drugs

Dora Akunyili was the Director-General of the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) from 2001 to 2008. During that time, she spearheaded a historic fight against fake pharmaceuticals in Nigeria (Okafor, 2014). She was quite passionate about this issue because she lost a sister to fake drugs. Under Akunyili's leadership, NAFDAC became an example of honesty and effectiveness which greatly reduced the number of fake medications in the country (Nwankwo, 2015). Akunyili's persistent dedication to public health and safety showed Gumi's values of moral integrity and fairness. She often had threats to her life but she stayed strong and won awards from all over the world including the Transparency International Integrity Award (Okafor, 2014). Her bravery and moral leadership set a standard for public service in Nigeria.

4. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala: Supporter of economic reforms and openness

Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala was Nigeria's Finance Minister twice and was a key player in getting Nigeria's \$18 billion in external debt cancelled which freed up money for the country's growth (Lewis, 2013). She developed the "Excess Crude Account," which assisted Nigeria's economy by saving oil money over a certain price (Okonjo-Iweala, 2012). Her changes made it easier for

people to see how the government was spending its money such as by making monthly revenue allocations to states openly. Okonjo-Iweala made history in 2021 when she became the first African and first woman to manage the World Trade Organisation (WTO). This showed that she is known across the world as a supporter of fair leadership and economic fairness (BBC News, 2021). Her focus on honesty, responsibility and fairness in society is in line with Gumi's moral beliefs showing how leaders can make the world a better place.

5. Nuhu Ribadu: A Model of Accountability and Anti-Corruption

Nuhu Ribadu, as the pioneer head of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) is often mentioned as an exemplar of accountability in Nigeria's public sector. Ribadu started a strong anti-corruption effort during his time in office (2003–2007) which led to the trial of famous people such as a former Inspector General of Police (Adebanwi, 2011). His work showed that Gumi stressed accountability, which means that leaders are seen as stewards who must be responsible for what they do. Ribadu's way of doing things was in line with Gumi's teachings that leaders should be honest and make sure that government is open (Gumi & Tsiga, 1992). Ribadu's bravery in standing up to powerful people especially in the political elite, is in line with Gumi's calls for moral courage and justice.

6. Olusegun Obasanjo: Mixed Legacy of Reform and Ethical Controversy

Olusegun Obasanjo was Nigeria's president from 1999 to 2007. He made a number of changes to make the government better such as setting up the EFCC and the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) (Adebanwi, 2012). These actions were in line with Gumi's values of being responsible and fighting corruption. Obasanjo also pushed for economic changes that helped Nigeria's economy thrive and cut down on its foreign debt. But there were some ethical problems with his government. His legacy was marred by claims of rigging elections, suppressing political dissent and abusing authority (Adebanwi, 2012). These discrepancies show that Obasanjo's activities were only partially in line with Gumi's teachings. For example, Obasanjo tried to make people more accountable yet sometimes his acts went against Gumi's moral code.

7. Sani Abacha: A Case of Ethical Contradiction

People often recall General Sani Abacha's time in power (1993–1998) for widespread corruption, breaches of human rights and the building up of personal riches at the expense of the Nigerian state (Smith, 2010). Reports say that Abacha and his friends stole billions of dollars from the national treasury (BBC News, 2006). These behaviours go against Gumi's ideas of moral leadership, responsibility and fairness. Gumi always spoke out against leaders who used their positions for personal benefit, calling it a breach of public trust and a violation of Islamic

moral principles (Gumi, 1984). Abacha was an authoritarian leader who put his own interests first, while Gumi was a moral leader who served others.

Evaluation of the Ethical Leadership Crisis in Nigeria

Nigeria is still dealing with a serious ethical leadership dilemma, even if there are leaders who have tried to live up to Gumi's moral standards. Research shows that corruption, nepotism and abuse of authority are still common which makes people less likely to trust the government (Asaju, Arome, & Mukaila, 2014). The Corruption Perceptions Index from Transparency International shows that Nigeria has always been one of the most corrupt countries in the world. This is a sign of a lack of ethical leadership (Transparency International, 2024).

One of the main problems is the difference between what leaders' say they will do and what they really do. Many Nigerian leaders talk about being open, fair and responsible in public yet their actions often show that they do not believe in these things. For example, several governments have promised to fight corruption but money from the public continues to be stolen. Gumi's warning about leaders who put their own interests ahead of the public good is still valid today as seen by the repeated examples of embezzlement and mismanagement in government.

Another problem is that many Nigerian leaders lack moral courage. Gumi said that moral leadership means having the guts to tell the truth and fight against injustice even if it puts your own safety at danger (Gumi & Tsiga, 1992). But in Nigeria, leaders who try to fight corruption or hold people accountable often have to deal with threats, political victimisation or exile (Adebanwi, 2012). This setting makes it hard for leaders to be honest and keeps a culture of complicity going.

Furthermore, the lack of means to hold leaders accountable has made the leadership issue much worse. Gumi preached that leaders are responsible to both God and the people. He called for open government and frequent public reporting (Gumi, 1984). But in Nigeria, a lot of politicians get away with what they do because of political favouritism and a weak legal system. Political interference, selective prosecution and a lack of political will can make it hard to hold corrupt leaders accountable.

The ongoing ethical leadership issue in Nigeria shows how important it is to change the way the country is run in a way that fits with Gumi's moral values. Nigerian leaders need to learn the ideals of justice, accountability, honesty and servant leadership that Gumi talked about. Using Gumi's teachings as a model, educational and leadership training programs can also be changed to focus on ethical leadership ideals.

Relevance of Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's Ethical Leadership to Nigerian Politics

Sheikh Abubakar Mahmud Gumi's ideas about ethical leadership which are based on fairness,

accountability and moral integrity, are still very important in Nigerian politics today. His principles give political leaders a moral foundation to follow in order to run the government in a fair, open and accountable way. Because Nigeria has a lot of problems with corruption, abuse of power and social injustice, using Gumi's ideas could make government much better and help people trust their leaders again (Gumi, 1984; Loimeier, 1997).

The idea of justice and fairness is one of the most important parts of Gumi's moral philosophy. He stressed that leaders must be fair and not show favouritism or discrimination when they administer justice. He quoted the Qur'an: "Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice" (Qur'an 4:58). In Nigeria, this principle can be used by making sure that official policies help all citizens no matter what their religion or ethnicity is. For example, social welfare programs, educational opportunities and public services should be fairly allocated so that different groups do not feel left out (Gumi, 1984).

Another important part of Gumi's thought is being open and responsible. Gumi said that leaders are stewards who have to answer to both the people and God for what they do (Loimeier, 1997). In real life, this implies that Nigerian officials should set up clear ways to handle public money, routinely report on their assets and be ready to explain their choices. Making anti-corruption groups like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) stronger and independent will help hold people accountable which reflect Gumi's taught (Yusuf, 2019). Gumi's model of ethical leadership was based on moral integrity. He said that leaders must be honest people whose personal character makes people trust them. This fits with the idea of servant leadership which says that leaders should put the needs of the people before their own. Leaders in Nigeria often utilise their public office to make money for themselves. Following Gumi's example of integrity can help restore people's faith in government (Gumi & Tsiga, 1992). Leaders should get frequent training on ethics and anyone who is found guilty of corruption should face the law no matter who they are.

Gumi also supported government that included everyone. He thought that leadership should not be restricted to one group but should include a variety of views such as women and young people. This point of view is quite important in Nigeria which is diverse and where politics are often affected by ethnic and religious differences. Promoting inclusive government can help bridge these gaps, build national unity and make sure that choices are made with the needs and wants of all citizens in mind (Loimeier, 1997).

Another part of Gumi's ideas that could improve Nigerian government is the idea of consultation (Shūrā). Gumi said that leaders should ask experienced people for input before making choices since this helps everyone learn and makes mistakes less likely (Gumi, 1984). In Nigeria, this can be made official by having frequent meetings with stakeholders to talk about important policy concerns. For example, community leaders, religious academics and civil society groups can take part in making decisions making sure that policies are based on a wide range of points of view.

Recommendations for Nigerian Political Leaders

It is very important to make ethical leadership training a part of the job for all Nigerian political leaders to align with Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's moral code. This kind of training should not just be a formality; it should be a full programme that focusses on justice, responsibility and moral integrity, which are Gumi's key values. The Nigerian Institute of Management and the National Institute for Policy and Strategic Studies (NIPSS) are two examples of political and civil service training schools that should include classes on ethical leadership, resolving conflicts and being accountable to the public. This method will give leaders the tools and information they need to run things honestly.

It is important to make accountability systems stronger so that public officials are held responsible for what they do. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) are two anti-corruption groups that should be able to look into and prosecute corruption without any political intervention. In addition, court processes should be hastened for cases involving corruption to guarantee that justice is served expeditiously. All elected and appointed officials should also have to publicly declare their assets and independent organisations should check and keep an eye on these statements.

Another important step towards making Nigeria's politics better is to encourage inclusive governance. Sheikh Gumi said that leaders should be like the people they serve. This involves developing rules that make sure women, young people and people from under-represented groups are included in decision-making processes. For example, political parties can use affirmative action to give women and young people a certain number of leadership posts (Obi, Paul, & Tisan, 2019). This will make sure that the decisions made by the government are in line with the hopes and needs of all residents.

Nigerian leaders also need to be open and honest in how they do business especially when it comes to managing public money. Government budgets should be made public in a clear way, including full details of income and expenses. To stop financial mismanagement, public procurement processes should be open, competitive and regularly audited. Also, Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala's idea of publishing monthly revenue allocations to states should be brought back to encourage openness. These steps will make people more confident in the government.

Another important recommendation is to encourage civic engagement. The government should make it easier for people to talk to their leaders, voice their concerns and give input on policy. This can be achieved through frequent town hall meetings, internet input platforms and community engagement programmes. Leaders can stay in touch with the people they lead by keeping lines of communication open. This is in accordance with Gumi's focus on consultation (Shūrā) and inclusion. People feel like they own and trust their leaders when they are involved in this way.

Finally, moral integrity should be a criterion that leaders in Nigeria cannot change. Political parties need to set strict

guidelines for how their candidates should act. This will make sure that only people with a history of honesty are nominated for public office. Parties should also set up ethics committees to keep an eye on how its members act and punish them for doing things that are wrong. In addition, the courts must make sure that leaders who are found guilty of corruption are quickly punished and given punishments that will stop other people from doing the same thing. People will trust the government again if they are committed to honesty.

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CONCLUSION

Sheikh Abubakar Gumi's concepts of ethical leadership which are based on fairness, accountability and moral integrity, provide a way to change how Nigeria is run for the better. His teachings stress that leaders should be fair, open, honest and receptive to the demands of the people. Nigerian leaders can build national unity, restore public trust and create a culture of ethical governance by following these rules. This study has shown that Gumi's ethical model is still useful for dealing with Nigeria's ongoing problems with leadership. It is an important guide for both public and political leaders.

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